

Sample 23a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0019
	{Si}	32.4
	{Fe}	20.4
	{Cl}	11.1
	{Al, Si}	5.7
	{Cl}	3.7
	{S, Ca}	3.3
	{Na, Si, Cl}	3.3
	{Si, Fe}	2.8
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	1.6
	{Ca}	1.6
	{Si, Cl}	1.2
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.9
	{Al, Si, K}	0.9
	{Mg, Si}	0.8
	{Si, Ca LoP}	0.7
	{Ti}	0.6
	{Na, Si}	0.6
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.5
	{Si, Ca HIP}	0.5
	{Al}	0.4
	{Mg, Ca}	0.4
	{Na, Cl, Fe}	0.4
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.4
	{Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Si, K}	0.3
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Al, Ca}	0.3
	{Si, Fe}	0.3
	{Cl, Fe}	0.2
	{Mg, Fe}	0.2
	{Mg}	0.2
	{S}	0.2
	{Mg, Cl}	0.2

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.9
Pellet	5.6
Ore preparation undifferentiated	10.5
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.0
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.6
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.2
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.5
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	1.9
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.2
Carbon rich - other	10.4
Cement or BOF converter	0.1
Cement	0.0
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.9
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.5
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	27.9
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	38.4
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.2
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.2

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	17.0
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	0.8
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.5
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	1.9
Site - carbon-rich other	1.2
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	10.4
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.1
Urban	1.4
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	27.9
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	38.4
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.4

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 23b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0013
	{Si}	34.7
	{Fe}	16.5
	{Cl}	11.3
	{Al, Si}	5.5
	{S, Ca}	4.0
	{Cl}	3.8
	{Na, Si, Cl}	3.3
	{Si, Fe}	2.5
	{Ca}	2.3
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	1.6
	{Si, Cl}	1.2
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.1
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.0
	{Al, Si, K}	0.8
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.8
	{Mg, Si}	0.7
	{Ti}	0.7
	{Na, Si}	0.7
	{Si, Ca HIP}	0.6
	{Mg, Ca}	0.5
	{Ca, Fe}	0.5
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.5
	{Na, Cl, Fe}	0.4
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.4
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.3
	{Al}	0.3
	{Cl, Fe}	0.2
	{Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Al, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, K}	0.2
	{Mg, Cl}	0.2
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{S}	0.2
	{Mg, Fe}	0.2

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	2.1
Pellet	3.6
Ore preparation undifferentiated	3.7
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.3
BOF converter slag	0.5
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.8
Desulph slag	0.2
Ca-aluminate slag	0.1
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.4
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.2
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	3.1
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.6
Carbon rich - other	20.4
Cement or BOF converter	0.1
Cement	0.0
Gypsum or anhydrite	1.0
Ti-rich paint	0.2
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.7
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	26.2
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	34.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.1
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.4

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	9.5
Site - ore / hot metal	0.3
Site - slag	1.5
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.4
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.2
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	3.1
Site - carbon-rich other	1.6
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	20.4
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.1
Urban	2.0
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	26.2
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	34.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 23c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0014
	{Si}	28.5
	{Fe}	18.0
	{Cl}	12.5
	{Al, Si}	6.1
	{Cl}	4.0
	{S, Ca}	4.0
	{Na, Si, Cl}	3.4
	{Si, Fe}	2.6
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	1.8
	{Ca}	1.6
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.5
	{Si, Cl}	1.2
	{Al}	1.1
	{Al, Si, K}	1.0
	{Si, Ca LoP}	0.8
	{Mg, Si}	0.7
	{Ti}	0.7
	{Na, Si}	0.7
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.6
	{Ca, Fe}	0.6
	{Al, Cl}	0.6
	{Si, Ca HiP}	0.5
	{Na, Cl, Fe}	0.5
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.4
	{Mg, Ca}	0.4
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.4
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.4
	{Na, Al, Cl}	0.4
	{Cl, Fe}	0.3
	{Si, Fe}	0.3
	{Mg, Fe}	0.2
	{Si, K}	0.2
	{Mg, Cl}	0.2
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.2

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	1.9
Pellet	5.6
Ore preparation undifferentiated	6.7
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.4
BOF converter slag	0.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.1
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.3
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.5
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	3.3
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.9
Carbon rich - other	12.7
Cement or BOF converter	0.1
Cement	0.0
Gypsum or anhydrite	1.3
Ti-rich paint	0.6
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	3.1
Salt or salt layer	0.1
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	25.6
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	35.7
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.3
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.3
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.3

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	14.2
Site - ore / hot metal	0.4
Site - slag	0.5
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.5
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.3
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	3.3
Site - carbon-rich other	0.9
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	12.7
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.1
Urban	5.0
Natural salt - immediate	0.1
Natural mineral background	25.6
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	35.7
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.3
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.6

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels